

Viscosity of *N*-Cetylpyridinium Chloride in Ethylene Carbonate and in Mixed Solvent of Ethylene Carbonate and Water at 40°

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Here we report our measurements at 40° of the viscosity of *N*-cetylpyridinium chloride (NCPC) at several concentrations below 0.05 *M* in ethylene carbonate (EC) and in mixed solvents of EC and water.

Results and Discussion

The plot of relative viscosity (η_{rel}) vs surfactant concentration in EC between 0.018 and 0.05 *M* shows a very sharp rise of η_{rel} almost from the lowest concentration 0.018 *M* used in this investigation. The sharp rise is followed by equally steep fall in a narrow concentration range 0.023–0.027 *M*. It is likely that some kind of association leading to micelle formation occurs in solution of NCPC in EC at concentration below 0.023 *M*. As is evident from sharp rise of η_{rel} the micelles in EC probably undergoes structural transition at around 0.023 *M*. Perte and coworkers¹ reported structural transition from sphere to rod-like in aqueous solution of cetylpyridinium bromide around second cmc. The reverse transition from rod-like to sphere is also reported in the literature. Lecithin is known to exist as rod-like micelles in aqueous solution. In presence of triglyceride, tributyrin, small angle neutron scattering studies indicate a transition from rod-like to spheres². If the micelles in solution of NCPC in EC are assumed to be rod-like, then this would occupy larger volume and its growth in EC below 0.023 *M* should accompany relatively sharp rise in η_{rel} as is actually found. As transition to spheres occurs, the obstruction to flow is less, leading decrease in η_{rel} followed by its gradual increase with surfactant concentration.

EC has a large dipole moment³ ($\mu = 4.87$ D), and the ionic head groups of the surfactant molecules are therefore directed towards the solvent molecules. Unlike water, EC is not a structured solvent. Because of the absence of hydrophobic interaction, the weak attraction, if any, between hydrocarbon tails will not be able to support spherical micellar shape. This will cause the hydrocarbon tails to arrange in rows forming rod-like micelles. With concentration, the hydrocarbon tails accumulate in the rod-like micelles and the simultaneous interaction between hydrocarbon tails within micellar boundary will give rise to net attractive pull in much the same way as the dense hard sphere gas⁴. This attractive pull within the micelle favours a transition from rod to sphere. Thus we may tentatively conclude that in EC, NCPC forms micelles with rod-like struc-

ture below 0.023 *M* which undergoes transition into spheres when the surfactant concentration exceeds this concentration.

Viscosity in mixed solvent of EC and water. Viscosity of NCPC between 0.005 and 0.24 *M* were measured at 40° in mixed solvent of compositions 24.6, 30.1, 46.4, 86.6 and 95.0% by weight of EC (Fig. 1) gives the plot of η_{rel} vs surfactant concentrations at various solvent compositions. It is seen that η_{rel} varies linearly with concentration upto around 0.1 *M* in NCPC in mixed solvent composition 24.6% of EC. The deviation from linearity occurs at increasingly lower concentration as the solvent becomes richer in EC. The profile in pure water retains its qualitative features unaltered in mixed solvent with EC as high as 86.6% by weight. Beyond this composition at ~95.0% of EC, there is a drastic change in the shape of the plot. In view of the smooth variation of viscosity (η) of solvent mixture with composition (figure not shown), the sudden change in the profile of the plot of η_{rel} vs surfactant concentration may be explained as arising due to the partial collapse of micellar structure. The water molecule may also form H-bond with EC and this process may compete with ion-dipole interaction at the micellar surface and reorganisation of micellar structure sets in.

In mixed solvent upto around ~86.6% of EC, the nature of the plot of η_{rel} vs surfactant concentration (NCPC) closely resembles that in pure water. There is conclusive evidence for the presence of micellar association of NCPC

Fig. 1. Plots of η_{rel} vs *C*.

in pure water. By comparison, therefore, we propose the existence of micellar association of NCPC in mixed solvent of EC and water as well. In pure EC, however, the shape of η_{rel} vs surfactant concentration (NCPC) is very unusual and a reasonable explanation seems to be a micellar transition from rod-like to spheres.

Experimental

NCPC (E. Merck) was used as such. EC (E. Merck) is solid at room temperature. The solvent was distilled under reduced pressure. The freshly distilled solvent had the following characteristics: $d = 1.3197 \text{ gm cm}^{-3}$ and $\eta = 1.909 \text{ cP}$ at 40° , which compared with the literature values^{3,5} ($d = 1.3208 \text{ gm cm}^{-3}$ and $\eta = 1.925 \text{ cP}$, 1.850 cP).

All measurements of density and viscosity were made in a thermostated water bath at $40.0 \pm 0.05^\circ$. A bicapillary pycnometer was employed for density determination. For

viscosity measurements two sets of Ostwald viscometer were employed having constants $K = 3.7964 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cS s}^{-1}$ and $L = 2.743 \text{ cS s}$ and $K = 3.6893 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cS s}^{-1}$ and $L = 0.208 \text{ cS s}$. Flow time was measured upto 1/10th of a second.

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